

Culturally Relevant Coding: an Experience in South India

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Abstract

After several years of developing creative computing projects in schools across South India, we have observed the importance of integrating local cultural elements into teaching and learning processes. During our recent stay in the Bangalore region as part of the Inventors4Change project, we carried out three activities aimed at connecting culturally significant elements from South India with concepts of creative coding and computational thinking. This article introduces the concept of Culturally Relevant Computing and provides a detailed description of the activities and their initial implementations in various schools and organizations. These efforts resulted in a total of nine workshops conducted in diverse contexts, involving different teams of educators and students of various age groups. The article also includes conclusions on the impact of employing Culturally Relevant Education in educational projects that use technologies for creative learning.

Keywords: Culturally Relevant Computing, Creative Coding, ICT in Education.

1 Introduction and context

Since 2009, the University of Girona has been implementing development cooperation projects in South India, with a particular focus on education. These projects have gone through various phases, and over the past fifteen years, the ecosystem of organizations and stakeholders in the Bangalore region (the capital of Karnataka state) involved in these initiatives has grown and consolidated. Led by the UdiGitalEdu research group, the projects received financial support from the University of Girona's Social Engagement Unit (previously known as the Cooperation Office).

The project began as an initiative to promote soft skills (creativity, critical thinking, and teamwork) through Educational Robotics (Muntaner-Perich, 2012) at a school called Shanti Bhavan, which focuses on providing quality education to Dalit children in the Bangalore area. During this initial phase, the approach shifted from a model centered on direct engagement with children to one that emphasized teacher training. The focus also transitioned from Educational Robotics to Maker Education (Muntaner-Perich et al., 2015). In addition to Shanti Bhavan, the project expanded to include four schools from the Parikrma Humanity Foundation located in different areas of Bangalore.

In a second phase, starting in 2013, collaborative projects were initiated between the participating Indian schools and several European schools. These efforts promoted Global Citizenship Education through the creation of collaborative digital stories (co-created by children from different schools and countries) aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals. The initiative served a dual purpose: fostering interculturality, global citizenship, and empathy, while also developing digital skills and critical knowledge such as coding. These projects highlighted the power of technology to bridge cultural gaps, encouraging students to engage with global issues in meaningful ways. This phase was made possible through the Inventors4Change and InventEUrs projects (Barikzai et al., 2015).

In a third phase, beginning in 2022, efforts focused on consolidating the ecosystem of schools and organizations that had been built over the years in Bangalore, fostering collaboration among them and creating spaces for dialogue. In July 2022, the Nimaya Fest was held at the Srishti Institute of Art, Design and Technology in Bangalore, coordinated by the University of Girona. The event brought together universities, schools, and NGOs, all of which shared an interest in exploring how technology can be used to promote creative learning in vulnerable communities. This phase emphasized sustainability, aiming to create a lasting network of partnerships that could support innovative educational practices in the region.

In 2024, with a stable ecosystem of collaborating organizations in Bangalore and fifteen years of experience in the region, the UdiGitalEdu group continues its commitment to education projects, placing greater emphasis on research and innovation for development. Within this context, the group decided to explore and investigate the concept of Culturally Relevant Computing (framed within the broader context of Culturally Relevant Education, CRE). As in the project's beginnings in 2009, the focus remains on finding ways to promote a creative, critical, and collaborative use of technology by children and teachers in schools devoted to educating the most vulnerable communities. However, the current approach emphasizes incorporating local cultural elements to create meaningful connections between students and the process of learning technology. The most recent visit to India (September 2024) was dedicated precisely to this topic and is the focus of this article. Ideas about Culturally Relevant Education and Computing are discussed in the following section.

2 Theoretical and Methodological Foundations

2.1 Culturally Relevant Education

Globalization and the expansion of the digital society have transformed contemporary societies, creating increasingly multicultural communities and posing a variety of challenges in contexts of growing diversity.

This phenomenon has significantly, though unevenly, affected all areas of social and institutional life, with a noticeable impact on schools, which have increasingly become multicultural microcosms within ever more diverse communities (Rodríguez and González, 2020, p.155).

Culturally Relevant Education (CRE) was introduced by Ladson-Billings and Allen and Booking in the 1990s in the United States. This model aims to address the multicultural nature of classrooms and the academic challenges often faced by students from diverse cultural backgrounds (Rodríguez and González, 2021). Specifically, it is based on the idea that teaching through the cultural context familiar to children can equitably improve educational outcomes.

CRE is rooted in constructivist theories that value diverse cultural perspectives, integrating ideas from critical, equity, and multicultural pedagogies (Rodríguez and González, 2021).

From a Vygotskian perspective, CRE is based, on one hand, on the concepts that students learn spontaneously through their informal experiences and, on the other, on the teachers' use of students' cultural heritage in the process of constructing new knowledge (Rodríguez and González, 2021, p.160).

Some studies (Aronson & Laughter, 2016; Au, 2007; Dover, 2013) highlight the objectives of CRE as follows: improving the academic success of culturally diverse students, establishing connections between school and family, strengthening competence in native culture and language, and promoting social justice, equality, and diversity. In other words, academic performance improves when educators successfully and meaningfully link their teaching methods to their students' cultural knowledge and practices.

CRE advocates breaking away from an ethnocentric view of teaching and encourages incorporating the cultural content brought in by the students themselves [...]. The goal is not to overload the curriculum with new content but to make it permeable to the cultural diversity of the educational community, recognizing that teaching is an activity shaped by culture (Rodríguez, 2011, p.166).

2.2 Culturally Relevant Computing

In the field of educational technologies, the underrepresentation of certain groups in computer science has spurred growing efforts to develop teaching approaches that better address the needs of a more diverse student population.

In this context, Culturally Relevant Computing (CRC) emerges as an evolving field of study that combines coding education with the research and established practices of CRE, aiming to create a computer science education that is both engaging and rigorous for underrepresented students. This educational approach is based on the premise that all children can acquire digital

skills and that this process is enhanced when they are encouraged to reflect on their identities and cultures (Raspberry Pi Computing Education Research Centre, 2023).

The role of educators in this approach is crucial, as they must create a learning environment that fosters such reflection, helping students understand the biases present in technological development and apply technology creatively to address issues that are meaningful to both themselves and their communities (Raspberry Pi Computing Education Research Centre, 2023).

The principles of CRE in the field of computing also aim to support the development of students' identities, encourage critical examination of inequalities in computer science, and address sociopolitical issues affecting the technological landscape (Madkins et al., 2020, p. 125).

2.3 Creative Computing

The workshops implemented in India have not only incorporated the principles of Culturally Relevant Computing but also integrated key principles of Technologies for Creative Learning.

The concept of Creative Computing is part of an approach that views technologies as a medium for creative expression and learning rather than merely a technical tool. This perspective draws from disciplines such as Constructionism, Maker Education, Computational Thinking, STEAM, and Tinkering, all interconnected and aimed at nurturing creativity in learning through the constructive use of technology.

Creative Computing, pioneered by Seymour Papert and further advanced by his disciple Mitchel Resnick, emerged as a method to leverage computers for fostering personal creativity and experimentation. Papert introduced LOGO, the first programming language specifically designed for children, which empowered students to build knowledge by creating digital artifacts (Papert, 1980). This concept later evolved into Scratch, a visual programming platform developed by Resnick and his team, enabling young people to craft interactive projects and express their creativity (Resnick, 2007).

Creative Computing focuses on developing computational thinking skills through the creation of meaningful and personal computing projects. In this paradigm, learning occurs collaboratively and exploratorily, with students engaging in the "creative thinking spiral", a process that involves imagining, creating, playing, sharing, reflecting, and reimagining. This cycle fosters autonomy and critical thinking, transforming students into creators rather than mere consumers of technology, while equipping them with essential skills to tackle real-life challenges.

Figure 1: Creative Thinking Spiral (Resnick, 2007)

Overall, this perspective of computing as a tool for self-expression and problem-solving enables deeper and more sustainable learning, where knowledge is actively constructed in an environment of support, creativity, and collaboration.

3 Field Implementations

During our most recent stay in Bangalore, we conducted three times each of the activities described below, across a variety of educational institutions in the city and its metropolitan area. These included both formal and informal education organizations, serving diverse audiences. Specifically:

- Parikrma Humanity Foundation manages four K-10 schools and a pre-university center in Bangalore, offering comprehensive, free education from early childhood to secondary school for children from underprivileged communities. In addition to academic instruction, Parikrma provides healthcare, and emotional and nutritional support, including three daily meals, aiming to transform the lives of these young individuals and their families. Its holistic approach seeks not only educational improvement but also integral development (Parikrma Humanity Foundation, 2024).
- Shanti Bhavan is a residential school in Tamil Nadu that provides free education from preschool to university for children from marginalized castes and groups. The school not only offers a strong academic foundation but also ensures a safe and structured environment where students receive housing, meals, and healthcare. Additionally, life skills are taught to prepare them for higher education and better job opportunities, helping them break the cycle of poverty (Shanti Bhavan, 2024).
- The Valley School, located in Bangalore, is an educational institution that follows the principles of philosopher Jiddu Krishnamurti. It provides education for children from privileged families, from early childhood to secondary level, emphasizing a holistic approach to human development. The school focuses on self-understanding, critical thinking, and a deep connection with nature, encouraging students to adopt an attitude of independent learning and creative exploration. The Valley School aims to cultivate responsible individuals who are self-aware and environmentally conscious, prepared to meet the challenges of the modern world (The Valley School, 2024).
- Paper Crane Lab is a creative community in Bangalore focused on teaching practical skills through crafts, technology, and art. Its goal is to inspire people of all ages to develop new abilities, fostering a culture of experimentation and creative collaboration within the DIY (Do It Yourself) movement (Paper Crane Lab, 2024).
- Fig Tree Learning Centre is a small non-profit organization that provides academic enrichment opportunities for children attending government schools in the village of Kasaghattapura, in northern Bangalore. Instead of adhering to a standard curriculum, the center offers additional activities designed to complement the formal education of its students (Fig Tree Learning Centre, 2024).
- The Museum of Art & Photography (MAP) in Bangalore explores the visual heritage of the Indian subcontinent through exhibitions ranging from traditional art to contemporary photography. By combining physical displays with digital experiences, MAP connects diverse audiences with India's artistic legacy, fostering cultural and educational dialogue (MAP Museum, 2024).

3.1 The Art of Kolams, Geometry and Creative Coding

This activity was conducted at Parikrma Koramangala School, The Valley School, and Shanti Bhavan with students ranging from fifth grade to tenth grade, depending on the institution.

The activity revolved around *kolams*, traditional geometric designs created in South India, typically on the ground at the entrances of homes using rice flour or colored powders. These patterns, composed of repetitive and symmetrical lines and dots, hold deep cultural and spiritual significance. They are believed to bring good luck, prosperity, and protection to the household. *Kolams* are predominantly made by women and represent both a daily act of devotion and an artistic expression.

After a brief introduction, the students, divided into teams, were asked to design and draw a *kolam*. They first sketched a draft on paper and then recreated it using colored chalk on the ground. They were given complete freedom to create any design they desired.

Figures 2 and 3: Students from Parikrma sketching and creating *kolams*

Once the *kolams* were completed, the children photographed them using digital tablets.

In the second part of the workshop, each team used the tablets to upload a photo of their *kolam* as a background in the Scratch or Octostudio applications (both are creative coding platforms designed for children). They were then given the task of programming an animation in which a character (either chosen or created by them) would follow the geometric shapes of their *kolam*, tracing lines over it.

Figures 4 and 5: Animations of characters created with Scratch and Octostudio following the geometric shapes of the *kolams*.

At the end of the activity, time was allocated for each team to share their work and present their animations to the rest of the group.

In these workshops, an effort was made to establish a connection between *kolams* —a cultural element deeply familiar to all the children, as they see them daily— and computational thinking, which they applied while programming with Scratch or Octostudio. The children worked on a range of skills, including artistic abilities, digital competencies, mathematical concepts (angles, distances, XY coordinates, etc.), and computational concepts (sequences, loops, etc.).

Additionally, the activity allowed for discussions about gender perspectives, as *kolams* are traditionally drawn by women. Both boys and girls participated equally in this activity, challenging traditional norms and fostering inclusivity.

3.2 Digital Stamping of Kalamkari Designs with Scratch

This workshop was implemented with primary school children in the lower and middle grades at Paper Crane Lab and with ninth and tenth-grade students at Parikrma Jayanagar School and The Valley School.

The activity focused on *kalamkari*, a traditional art form from the state of Andhra Pradesh in South India, which involves applying designs and patterns to cotton textiles. Originally, designs were hand-painted using a pen-like tool (*kalam*), but over time, carved wooden blocks were also used as stamps.

The session started with a brief introduction to *kalamkari*, after which the children, working in teams, designed and drew patterns. The idea was to photograph their designs and use them for digital stamping with Scratch.

First, the children sketched their patterns with pencils on paper, then selected their favorite designs to color and took photos of them using a digital tablet. The challenge was to create an animation where their design was repeatedly stamped across the screen. If there was enough time, they could design a digital character and use their pattern to decorate its clothing or adapt an existing Scratch project to stamp a *saree* with their design.

To conclude the activity, each team presented their *kalamkari* animation to the rest of the group, sharing their discoveries and creative processes.

Figures 6 and 7: A participant in the workshop at Paper Crane Lab creating designs and using Scratch for digital stamping.

In these workshops, an effort was made to establish a connection between the *kalamkari* tradition and the computational thinking used to program digital stamping with Scratch. The children worked across disciplines, developing artistic skills, digital competencies, mathematical concepts such as symmetry and randomness, and computational concepts (sequences, loops, etc.).

Figure 8: A final result showcasing a saree digitally stamped with a custom design.

3.3 Illuminating Women Through Art and Technology: Tholu Bommalata (Shadow Puppetry)

This educational activity was implemented at the Fig Tree Learning Centre with children aged six to twelve, and at the MAP Museum in an open workshop for adults as well as ninth- and tenth-grade students from Parikrma Sahakarnagar and Nandini Layout schools.

The activity was inspired by traditional shadow theatre performances using puppets, known as *tholu bommalata*, originating from the Indian states of Andhra Pradesh and Telangana. This tradition employs large, colorful puppets made from leather, which are manipulated to narrate epic stories from Indian mythology, such as the Ramayana and the Mahabharata. For generations, the Aare Kapu community has preserved this art form, passing down their knowledge and skills to their descendants. These performances typically take place during major festivals and are accompanied by traditional music, creating a captivating spectacle that combines craftsmanship, storytelling, and music.

Figure 9: Parikrma students during their visit to the “Visible/Invisible Women” exhibition.

After visiting the "Visible/Invisible Women" exhibition at the MAP Museum, which included examples of *tholu bommalata*, workshop participants were invited to imagine and create a story as a team, either reinterpreting one of the works seen in the museum or drawing inspiration from a traditional legend. In the version of the workshop conducted at the Fig Tree Learning Center, the tradition of *tholu bommalata* was introduced, and a more accessible theme was proposed, focusing on animals, given the age of the participants.

Once each team agreed on their narrative, they began sketching the designs for their puppets on paper. They then constructed the puppets using the available craft materials, paying special attention to the mechanics that would allow articulated movement.

Figures 10, 11, and 12: Process of creating articulated puppets at Fig Tree Learning Center.

Next, each group was provided with a digital tablet equipped with the Octostudio application. Using this, they photographed their characters and created an animation that represented or complemented the story they had previously imagined.

Finally, the participants shared their stories with the other groups by presenting their Octostudio project or by having their tangible and digital characters interact.

Figures 13 and 14: Adults creating their final product and sharing their creations, outcomes of the workshop at the MAP Museum.

In these workshops, both the experience of the exhibition and the children's prior knowledge about animals were leveraged to inspire them to create or rewrite a story. This approach fostered the need to apply computational thinking to animate their stories, while also developing critical thinking, teamwork, creativity, and computational concepts such as sequences and loops.

4 Conclusions

The concept of Culturally Relevant Computing has proven to be an effective strategy for fostering meaningful learning among students from vulnerable communities in Bangalore. During the implementations, profound connections were observed between students and educational content by integrating programming and technology instruction with local cultural elements such as *kolams*, *kalamkari*, and *tholu bommalata*.

These activities not only helped students develop digital skills and computational thinking but also allowed them to explore and appreciate their cultural heritage. An interdisciplinary learning environment was created by combining artistic skills with technological and computational concepts, enriching the overall educational experience. By linking familiar cultural practices to computational thinking, students approached technology as a tool for both personal expression and academic growth.

Additionally, incorporating traditional cultural practices promoted equity in the classroom and addressed gender perspectives. For instance, involving both boys and girls in creating *kolams* — a practice traditionally performed by women— challenged and expanded participants' understanding of gender roles.

Our workshop with adults at the MAP Museum, focusing on the traditional shadow puppet art of *tholu bommalata*, was particularly enriching. This workshop demonstrated that the principles of culturally relevant computing could extend beyond childhood and youth education, proving equally effective in adult learning contexts. By exploring the intersection of modern technology and cultural traditions, participants showed high levels of interest and engagement. The activity allowed them to reconnect with their artistic skills while learning new digital skills using tools like OctoStudio.

Ongoing research and adaptation of this approach in collaboration with local communities, educators, and organizations are essential for future success. The ability to incorporate cultural practices into technology education in ways that are both relevant and empowering for students will determine the sustainability and long-term impact of these projects.

Among the potential future work, we highlight the following:

- Research and design workshops that incorporate other local cultural expressions such as traditional music, dance, storytelling, or crafts.
- Implement workshops that foster dialogue among the diverse cultures present in the intervention.
- Train and empower local educators: Develop training programs for teachers in culturally relevant education methodologies and their integration with technology. This would enable local educators to sustain and expand these practices, ensuring the longevity of the project.
- Study long-term educational impact: Conduct longitudinal studies to evaluate the effects of these initiatives on students' academic performance and their development of digital and socio-emotional skills.
- Develop open educational resources: Create instructional materials and implementation guides available online so that other educators and organizations can replicate and adapt these practices to their own contexts.

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